

PROCESSING, STRUCTURE and PROPERTIES OF NOVEL POLYMER NANOCOMPOSITE FOAMS

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INTRODUCTION

Polymeric foams are used in many applications because of their excellent strength-to-weight ratio, good thermal and sound insulation properties, and materials savings, etc ^[1]. Foams with nanometer sized voids are being under investigation for potential applications as the next generation materials of low dielectric constants ^[2]. However, compared to bulk polymers, foams have reduced mechanical strength and lower dimensional and thermal stability. Recently developed microcellular foams provide improved mechanical properties over conventional foams^[3], but they require stringent processing conditions (e.g., very high pressure and pressure drop rate, and processing temperature close to the glass transition temperature) ^[4, 5]. This limits the operating window for extrusion and the attainable size of foam products.

Addition of a small amount of clay nanoparticles into polymer matrices provides significant improvement in a wide variety of properties ^[6-8]. Montmorillonite (MMT) is the most widely used clay in nanocomposite synthesis. The individual clay particles possess a platelet-like structure, in which the thickness dimension is ~1 nm and the lateral dimensions are up to ~1 μ m. This high aspect ratio and large surface area offer the potential for high reinforcing efficiency, good barrier properties, and improved dimensional and thermal stability. The nanometer dimension is especially beneficial for reinforcing foam materials considering the thickness of foam cell walls is in the micron and submicron regime. Additionally, nanoparticles may serve as nucleation agents for bubble generation. The extremely fine dimensions and large surface area of nanoparticles provides much more intimate contact between the particles, polymer matrix, and gas. Further, a significantly higher effective particle concentration can be achieved at a low nominal particle concentration. Both could lead to improved nucleation efficiency.

However, the highest enhancement in property improvement and nucleation efficiency can only be realized when the nanoparticles are dispersed uniformly (exfoliated) in the polymer matrix. In the natural state MMT platelets are held together by van der Waals forces and electrostatic forces to form crystallites (tactoids). Organic cationic surfactants, e.g., alkyl ammonium salts, are commonly used to modify the negatively charged clay surface through ion exchange, in order to improve wetting and lower the interfacial tension between the polymer and clay that in turn enhances dispersion. Favorable interactions between the polymer matrix and clay surface and the resulting energy reduction are critical for the formation of exfoliated nanocomposites ^[9, 10]. Although highly desirable, exfoliation is challenging and requires fine tuning of the clay surface chemistry as well as synthesis and processing conditions. The less desirable but more attainable structure is an intercalated particle dispersion, where polymer chains penetrate into the interlayer region of clays to form nanocomposite without totally disrupting the crystallites.

In this study, we synthesized a series of polystyrene (PS) and poly(methyl methacrylate) (PMMA) MMT nanocomposites possessing either intercalated or exfoliated structure. These nanocomposites were foamed via a batch process using an environmentally benign solvent, carbon dioxide, as the foaming agent. The effects of clay dispersion, as well as polymer-clay surface- CO₂ interaction, on the foam cell morphology are investigated.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials Methylmethacrylate (MMA), Styrene (St) and 2,2'-azobisisobutyronitrile (AIBN) were purchased from Aldrich. PS (CX 5197) is from AtoFina Petrochemicals, while PMMA (PL25) is from Plaskolite. Two types of organically modified MMT clays were used. Cloisite 20A (20A) is a MMT modified by dimethyl dihydrogenated tallowalkyl ammonium onium cations (Southern Clay Products). Na⁺-MMT (cation exchange capacity 92.4 milliequivalent/100g, from Southern Clay Products) was modified using a reactive cationic surfactant 2-methacryloyloxyethylhexadecyldimethyl ammonium bromide (MHAB) via ion-exchange reaction ^[11]. The resulting organoclay is denoted as MHABS. Polymer/20A nanocomposites were prepared using a Leistritz ZSE-27 intermesh twin-screw extruder (L/D= 40, d= 27 mm) in co-rotating mode between 200-220°C and 200 rpm screw speed. In-situ polymerization was carried out to prepare PMMA and PS/MHABS nanocomposites. The monomer, MHABS, and AIBN (0.5% by weight) were mixed using a high shear mixer. The mixture was reacted isothermally (60°C for styrene, 50°C for MMA) for 20 hrs, after which the temperature was raised to 105°C for another 30 min. A two-stage method was also used to prepare PS/MHABS nanocomposites. First a 20% nanocomposite masterbatch was prepared by in-situ polymerization. It was then blended with neat PS to prepare nanocomposites with desired clay concentration using a DACA microcompounder at 200°C and 250 rpm. Soxhlet extraction was used to extract un-bonded PMMA from PMMA/MHABS nanocomposites, using dichloromethane as the solvent. The un-extractable portion consists of MHABS and a substantial amount of PMMA (64% of the total weight of the un-extractable nanocomposite). The resulting material was blended with neat PS to produce PS/(MHABS/PMMA). (PS/MHABS)/PMMA was prepared via blending a PS/MHABS nanocomposite with PMMA. These two materials have the same weight composition (PS/PMMA/MHABS=86/9/5).

Foaming of Nanocomposites The foaming agent, bone-dry grade carbon dioxide, was provided by Praxair. Samples were placed in a stainless steel vessel and CO₂ was delivered via a syringe pump. The system was allowed to equilibrate at the foaming temperature and pressure for sufficient time to ensure equilibrium. The pressure was then rapidly released and the foam cells were fixed by cooling with an ice and water mixture. Alternatively, samples were saturated at sub-ambient temperature (0°C) after which they were taken out and placed in a water bath (80°C) to produce foams. After foaming, the foam structure was again fixed by an ice water mixture.

Characterization Clay dispersion in polymers is characterized by transmission electron microscopy (TEM). Image was obtained from a Phillip CM12 using an accelerating voltage of 80 kV. Samples were microtomed at room temperature with a diamond knife and mounted on a 200 mesh copper grid. A Phillip XL30 scanning electron microscope (SEM) was used to observe the foam cell morphology. Samples were freeze-fractured in liquid nitrogen and the fracture surface was sputter-coated with gold before observation. Image analysis was performed on the SEM micrographs using Scion Image software to obtain the average cell size and cell density ^[5].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Two types of organically modified clays, a commercially available Cloisite 20A (20A) and custom modified MHABS, are used to fabricate nanocomposites (see experimental section). Shown in Figure 1(a) is a TEM micrograph of a PS/5%20A nanocomposite (the dark lines are the fringes of individual clay layers). Wide angle x-ray diffraction (WAXD) (not shown here) reveals the (d001) basal spacing increases from 2.3 nm to 3.4 nm upon PS intercalation. Large clay aggregates are present in the matrix. On the other hand, exfoliated PS nanocomposites can be synthesized for clay concentration as high as 20 wt% by using MHABS, as verified by TEM micrograph shown in Figure 1(b). The tactoids have been completely delaminated and uniformly dispersed in the matrix. Most clay layers are present as single or double layers, while stacks of multiple layers, being widely separated, are also observable in some regions. MHAB contains a reactive methacrylate group and is able to copolymerize with vinyl monomer. The growing polymer chain inside the clay gallery pushes the layers apart and leads to eventual delamination of the crystallites ^[11]. Also notable is that the exfoliated structure in PS/MHABS nanocomposites is stable after further processing such as extrusion and injection molding. Shown in Figure 1(c) is a TEM micrograph of a PS/5wt% nanocomposite after extrusion and injection molding. The nanocomposite was prepared by a two-stage method (see experimental section). PMMA/20A and PMMA/MHABS nanocomposites were also synthesized and their respected TEM micrographs are shown in Figures 1(d) and (e), respectively. Similar to PS, PMMA/MHABS leads to exfoliated nanocomposites while PMMA/20A exhibits intercalated morphology, with a (d001) basal spacing of 3.6 nm (from WAXD).

Figure 1. TEM images of nanocomposites: (a) PS/5%20A; (b)PS/20%MHABS; (c)PS/5%MHABS; after extrusion and injection molding; (d) PMMA/5%20A; (e) PMMA/5%MHABS.

PS and PS/5wt% clay nanocomposites were foamed at 120°C and CO₂ pressure of 13.8 MPa. The foam cell morphology is shown in Figures 2(a)-(c). With the addition of clay, the cell size decreases and the cell density increases. In the presence of 5% 20A, the cell size decreases from 20.0 μm to 15.2 μm, and the cell density increases from 8.23×10⁷ cells/cm³ to 1.31×10⁸ cells/cm³. The exfoliated nanocomposite

Figure 2. SEM images of foams (a) PS; (b) PS/5%20A; (c)PS/5%MHABS; (d) PMMA; (e) PMMA/5%20A; (f) PMMA/5%MHABS, (g) (PS/MHABS)/PMMA, (h) PS/(MHABS/PMMA)

Pa. The morphology of the PMMA/20A nanocomposite has a cell size of $5.4 \mu\text{m}$, smaller than that of pure PMMA foam ($8.2 \mu\text{m}$). At the same time, cell density increases from $1.62 \times 10^9 \text{ cells/cm}^3$ (pure PMMA foam) to $4.22 \times 10^9 \text{ cells/cm}^3$. The PMMA/MHABS nanocomposite foam exhibits dramatically smaller cell size ($1.7 \mu\text{m}$) and higher cell density ($1.51 \times 10^{11} \text{ cells/cm}^3$).

around $4.02 \times 10^8 \text{ cells/cm}^3$. Clay undoubtedly cell density can be qualitatively described by equation, the nucleation rate is expressed as $\frac{dN}{dt} = C_1 \exp\left(-\frac{U}{RT}\right) \exp\left(-\frac{K_g}{R(T-\Delta T)f}\right)$, where C_1 is the Boltzmann's constant, T is the temperature. The interfacial tension σ , contact angle θ at the interface is expressed by the following relation: $\cos \theta = \frac{\sigma_{ps} - \sigma_{ps/clay}}{\sigma_{ps}}$. For intercalated nanocomposites, most of the clay is in the form of stacks of a few layers. Usually the distance between the layers is about 1 nm , which is much smaller than the length of a polymer chain. Many more clay platelets are in direct contact with the polymer chain, providing a much larger interfacial area for CO_2 adsorption and bubble nucleation. The nucleation rate is substantially higher, resulting in a higher cell density. While more cells nucleate, a similar amount of gas is available for bubble growth, leading to a reduction of cell size.

PMMA foam has much smaller cell size and higher cell density than PS foam. It is well known that CO_2 has much higher solubility in PMMA than in PS due to the strong interaction between CO_2 and the carbonyl groups in PMMA [14, 15]. This leads to an increase of homogeneous nucleation rate [16]. To more clearly illustrate the heterogeneous nucleation effect of clays in these two polymers, the cell densities of

PS and PMMA nanocomposite foams are normalized to those of their respective pure polymer foams as shown in Table 1.

Table 1 Comparison of Cell Density

PMMA series	normalized cell density	PS series	normalized cell density
PMMA	1.0	PS	1.0
5%20A	2.6	5%20A	1.6
5%MHABS	93.5	5%MHABS	4.9

Addition of 5wt% 20A has a similar effect on cell density for both PMMA and PS. However, the increase of cell density is significantly higher for PMMA than for PS when 5% MHABS is present. The former has a cell density more than 90 times higher than the pure PMMA foam, while the latter shows only a five fold increase in cell density over pure PS foam.

The difference of available nucleation sites is not expected to cause this dramatic difference, as MHABS is well dispersed in both PS and PMMA matrices. A plausible mechanism could be that there is a substantial difference of polymer-particle-CO₂ interaction at the interface, which could lead to a difference in reduction of the nucleation free energy. In both nanocomposites, exfoliation is achieved through copolymerization of the interlayer surfactant MHAB and vinyl monomer, leading to the growing polymer end-tethered on the clay surface. The main difference between the copolymers tethered on the clay surface in PMMA/MHABS and that in PS/MHABS is that in PMMA/MHABS, the copolymer is essentially PMMA with a cationic ammonium head group bonded to the clay surface, whereas the copolymer in PS/MHABS is a PS polymer containing one methacrylic group. The former has a much higher affinity to CO₂ due to the interaction between CO₂ and the carbonyl groups in PMMA^[14, 15]. More CO₂ is likely to be attracted to the surface to form nuclei. More importantly, a strong affinity between CO₂ and the carbonyl group of the tethered copolymers in PMMA/MHABS may reduce the gas-particle interfacial tension and consequently the contact angle. This would lead to the reduction in nucleation free energy and a large increase of nucleation rate.

To validate this hypothesis, the following two materials were prepared and foamed at 120°C and CO₂ pressure of 13.8 MPa: (PS/MHABS)/PMMA and PS/(MHABS/PMMA) (see experimental section). Morphology of the two foams is shown in Figures 2(g) and (h). The former has a cell size of 11.1 μm and a cell density of 6.25×10⁸ cells/cm³, whereas the latter has a smaller cell size (8.8 μm), and cell density almost two times higher (1.23×10⁹ cells/cm³). WAXD data shows that clay remains exfoliated in the former, whereas the latter possesses the intercalated structure with a basal spacing of 3.2 nm (after extraction of free PMMA, the exfoliated structure collapsed. Subsequent blending with PS only yielded intercalated nanocomposites). The other major difference between these two nanocomposites is that PMMA is located at clay surface in PS/(MHABS/PMMA), but dispersed in PS matrix in (PS/MHABS)/PMMA to form distinct domains. As a result, (PS/MHABS)/PMMA is opaque, while PS/(MHABS/PMMA) is transparent, even though the two nanocomposites have the same compositions. Although PS/(MHABS/PMMA) has fewer nucleation sites (being intercalated), it yields a higher cell density. This increase can primarily be attributed to reduction of the nucleation free energy as a result of the presence of PMMA at the polymer-clay-CO₂ interface. In PMMA/MHABS, the exfoliated structure ensures the highest number of available nucleation sites, and the interfacial PMMA at clay surface leads to the reduction of the nucleation free energy. A combination of these two factors results in the extremely high nucleation efficiency as observed in Figure 2(f) and Table 1.

CO₂ solubility in polymers, which temperature and pressure), can be utilized to increase cell density. Shown in Figure 3 is a SEM image of a PMMA/5%MHABS foam saturated at 0°C and 3.45 MPa and foamed at 80°C. The average cell size is around 0.3 μm and the cell density around 1.86 × 10¹⁰ cells/cm³.

changing the saturation conditions (i.e. temperature and pressure), can be utilized to increase cell density. Shown in Figure 3 is a SEM image of a PMMA/5%MHABS nanocomposite foam saturated at 0°C and 3.45 MPa and foamed at 80°C. The average cell size is around 0.3 μm and the cell density around 1.86 × 10¹⁰ cells/cm³.

Figure 3. SEM of a PMMA/5%MHABS foam. Sample was saturated with CO₂ at 0°C and 3.45 MPa and foamed at 80°C

The nanocomposite foams exhibit greatly improved mechanical properties and they will be presented at the meeting.

CONCLUSIONS

We have developed a method to synthesize exfoliated PMMA and PS clay nanocomposites. In the case of PS/clay nanocomposites, exfoliation can be achieved for clay concentration as high as 20% by weight. The exfoliated structure is preserved after extrusion. Both intercalated and exfoliated PMMA and PS/clay nanocomposites foams were prepared using supercritical CO₂ as the foaming agent. Presence of a small amount of clay nanoparticles greatly reduces foam cell size and increases cell density. Exfoliated nanocomposites yield foams with the smallest cell size and the highest cell density. Cell morphology can be further manipulated by adjustment of polymer-clay surface-CO₂ interaction and foaming conditions to achieve microcellular and sub-microcellular foams. The high nucleation efficiency can produce microcellular nanocomposite foams at less stringent processing conditions, leading to cost savings and processing flexibility.

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